

Unpacking juiciness in plant-based meat alternatives: a temporal sensory investigation of texture during mastication

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ABSTRACT

Texture, particularly juiciness, remains a critical barrier to consumer acceptance of plant-based meat alternatives. This study examined how the perception of juiciness evolves dynamically during mastication and how formulation strategies influence texture compared with an animal-based reference. Nine samples were evaluated: eight plant-based formulations (varying in fat type and emulsifier content) and one beef control. A trained panel ($n = 10$) assessed mechanical, geometrical, and surface texture attributes after 5 and 10 chews. Consumers ($n = 109$) provided liking ratings, completed a Temporal Check-All-That-Apply (TCATA), and supplied background information.

The beef patty was perceived by the trained panel as significantly juicier, firmer, chewier, and greasier than plant-based samples, which were drier, crumblier, and more fracturable. Consumer TCATA profiles showed persistent dominance of dryness and crumbliness for plant-based patties throughout chewing, indicating an early and sustained loss of juiciness during mastication. These results highlight that the timing and persistence of moisture release, rather than static composition, drive perceived texture performance.

Consumer segmentation nevertheless indicated heterogeneity in sensitivity to juiciness loss and fragmentation. Three consumer segments differed in sensitivity to texture, ranging from meat-attached consumers preferring juicy, coarse textures to more plant-oriented consumers tolerant of drier, grainier profiles; these differences aligned with oral processing style, with “chewers” dominating beef-oriented segments and “crunchers” more prevalent among plant-based-preferring consumers.

Overall, a substantial texture gap remains between plant-based and beef patties, driven by insufficient and unstable juiciness. Addressing this gap requires targeting not only composition but the temporal dynamics of moisture release, while accounting for consumer variability.

1. Introduction

The global shift toward more sustainable and flexitarian eating patterns has intensified the development of plant-based meat alternatives (PBMA). Despite rapid product expansion, repeat purchase remains limited, often due to sensory shortcomings, particularly in texture and mouthfeel (Giacalone et al., 2022). Indeed, consumer rejection in this product category is frequently tied to textural deficiencies such as

dryness, crumbliness, and lack of juiciness, especially when products are benchmarked against animal-based controls (Forster et al., 2024; Ilic et al., 2025). Key mouthfeel attributes, particularly juiciness and the characteristic breakdown of muscle fibers during mastication, remain difficult to replicate with plant-based formulations and continue to constrain widespread consumer acceptance (Giacalone et al., 2022). Nevertheless, recent reviews have noted that “texture” is often described only in general terms in the PBMA sensory literature, with insufficient

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attention to specific textural attributes such as juiciness, cohesiveness, or fibrousness (Andreani et al., 2023; Konrad et al., 2024). This lack of specificity limits both our mechanistic understanding and the actionability of previous findings. Food texture is a multidimensional sensory concept that, according to ISO standards (ISO 11036, 2020; ISO 5492, 2009), encompasses mechanical, geometrical, body and surface characteristics perceived during oral processing. Building on this foundation, Bondu et al. (2022) proposed the *Texture Wheel*, a structured framework that classifies texture into: (1) mechanical properties (e.g., hardness, chewiness, cohesiveness), describing how foods resist deformation and break down during chewing; (2) geometrical properties (e.g., graininess, fibrousness, particle size), reflecting the spatial arrangement of the food matrix; and (3) surface and body attributes (e.g., juiciness, dryness, oiliness, mouth coating), capturing lubrication, moisture release, and interactions with oral surfaces. These categories are consistent with the seminal perspective of Szczesniak (2002), who argued that texture is not merely a set of physical measurements, but a perceptual phenomenon shaped by multisensory integration during eating and increasingly understood as emerging dynamically throughout oral processing rather than reflecting material properties alone (Chen, 2026).

This comprehensive view is particularly relevant for plant-based meat analogues, where structure, hydration, and fat behavior all influence perceived texture and mouthfeel and ultimately drive consumer acceptance or rejection in this product category. Juiciness is consistently reported as a critical sensory attribute for consumer satisfaction in burgers but remains difficult to replicate in plant-based products due to the unique structure of animal meat, which naturally retains and releases moisture during chewing (Varela et al., 2022; Xu & Falsafi, 2023). To address these issues, producers rely on additives and formulation strategies to improve texture. While these sometimes involve trade-offs, for instance, a perception of these foods as ‘ultra-processed’ in the public discourse, they remain central to PBMA development (Rune et al., 2022; Starowicz et al., 2022; Starowicz et al., 2022; Varela et al., 2022). Compared with animal fats, many plant-based fats have different melting properties and structural organization, which can alter lubrication and reduce perceived juiciness in PBMA (McClements, 2024; St. Pierre & Kuhl, 2024; Xue et al., 2025; Gao et al., 2025). These fat-system differences are considered a key contributor to the juiciness deficit when PBMA are benchmarked against beef patties (Brouwer et al., 2025; Xue et al., 2025).

Emulsification is a widely used strategy in PBMA to stabilize fat–water distributions and support structural cohesion during cooking (Jang & Lee, 2024; Kyriakopoulou et al., 2021). However, if emulsifier level is too high, water may become overly immobilized within the matrix, reducing fluid release during mastication and lowering perceived juiciness (Rudge et al., 2025; Zhang et al., 2025).

Despite these established mechanisms, the specific contributions of fat type (plant vs animal) and emulsifier concentration to dynamic lubrication and juiciness perception remain insufficiently understood in PBMA, as most studies rely on static end-point measurements rather than time-resolved analyses (Zhang et al., 2025; Brouwer et al., 2025; Xue et al., 2025), despite growing recognition that sensory texture perception emerges dynamically during oral processing rather than as a fixed property measurable outside the eating context (Chen, 2026).

As highlighted by Zhang et al. (2025), is an integrated percept arising from multiple interacting sensory cues. It includes initial juiciness, the moisture perceived at first bite (linked to immediate water/fat release); sustained juiciness, describing the lubrication and moistness perceived during chewing; and final juiciness, referring to wetness at the point of swallowing or lingering residue. These dynamic stages unfold during mastication and are influenced by matrix composition, fat behavior, and saliva interaction (McClements, 2024; Zhang et al., 2025), with food–saliva interactions playing a central role in lubrication, particle aggregation, and bolus cohesion during oral processing (Mosca & Chen, 2017). Oral processing itself involves sequential stages including comminution, saliva incorporation, bolus formation, and swallowing

(Chen, 2009), through which juiciness perception evolves dynamically during mastication. By integrating temporal sensory analysis, researchers can track how juiciness evolves throughout mastication, providing deeper insight into how structural properties influence moisture release and mouthfeel over time. However, many sensory studies on PBMA often focus exclusively on instrumental measurements or on end-point consumer performance metrics (e.g. liking or purchase intent), with limited attention to how texture unfolds dynamically during oral processing, a methodological gap highlighted in recent sensory and formulation reviews (Imran & Liyan, 2023; Marczak & Mendes, 2024). Capturing how these sensory attributes evolve requires dynamic methodologies. This includes methods such as Temporal Dominance of Sensation (TDS) (Pineau & Schlich, 2023) and Temporal Check-All-That-Apply (TCATA) (Castura, Antúnez, Giménez & Ares, 2016) which allow the tracking of changes in perception over time, providing insight into when sensations like juiciness or dryness appear, peak, and decline (Zhang et al., 2025; Moss et al., 2023). However, such temporal methods to date remain severely underutilized in the study of PBMA (Giacalone, 2025).

Importantly, texture and mouthfeel are intertwined with other oral sensations. In particular, flavor release, in terms of overall intensity rather than identity, contributes to perceptions of richness and lubrication (McClements, 2024). Basic taste attributes, especially umami in this context, can enhance the perception of juiciness and fullness, contributing to consumer satisfaction (Starowicz et al., 2022; Xu & Falsafi, 2023). Umami has also been shown to reinforce moistness and mouth-coating effects in plant-based foods, compensating for low-fat formulations and increasing hedonic response (Sakai et al., 2025).

Another important consideration is that since these products are intended to replace meat, benchmarking against relevant animal-based references is essential to identify which sensory dimensions remain lacking (Giacalone, 2025). Forster et al. (2024) showed that animal-based patties had higher intensities of juiciness and cohesiveness based on descriptive sensory analysis, while Ilic et al. (2025) found that consumers rated these samples more favorably in terms of overall texture and liking, particularly during the later stages of mastication. Nevertheless, such direct comparisons remain surprisingly limited in the literature, and studies linking specific formulation strategies, such as fat source and emulsifier level, to temporal texture perception are scarce. A more systematic understanding of how formulation parameters influence the dynamic sensory experience is needed to close the texture gap between plant-based and animal-based patties.

Finally, product-level drivers of texture and juiciness alone cannot fully explain consumer acceptance; understanding how individual differences shape perception is equally critical. Because juiciness perception unfolds dynamically during mastication, differences in how consumers experience and evaluate these temporal sensory cues may further shape acceptance outcomes. Previous experience and familiarity with PBMA can influence sensory expectations and acceptance (Hoek et al., 2011; Onwezen et al., 2021), while individual differences in oral processing behavior, i.e. how consumers manipulate food during chewing (Jeltema et al., 2016), may directly affect texture perception and the temporal release of juiciness. Psychological factors also warrant attention: food neophobia (Flight et al., 2003) and meat attachment (Graça et al., 2015) have been shown to predict PBMA acceptance, and emerging evidence suggests that categorical rejection, driven by beliefs about unnaturalness, low sensory quality, or social norms, constitutes a distinct barrier (Michel et al., 2021; Wassmann et al., 2025). Despite recognition that these perceptual, behavioural, and psychological differences influence response to PBMA (Hoek et al., 2011; Onwezen et al., 2021), few studies systematically account for them when evaluating texture perception. This gap underscores the need for segmentation approaches that capture heterogeneity in consumer responses to these products.

Against this background, the objective of this study was to advance understanding of how juiciness perception unfolds dynamically during

mastication using temporal sensory evaluation. Plant-based burger patties varying in protein source, fat type, and emulsifier level were used as sensory stimuli to examine how compositional differences influence the temporal sensory experience of texture and juiciness-related mouthfeel, captured through attributes including juiciness, dryness, mouth coating, and fatty sensation. By characterising temporal sensory changes during mastication, the study provides insight into how formulation strategies are reflected in perceived juiciness over the course of oral processing, and how plant-based products compare with an animal-based reference. In addition, consumer segmentation was applied as an interpretive framework to explore whether these temporal sensory perceptions are experienced and valued differently across consumers with distinct behavioural and attitudinal profiles. Two complementary research questions (RQs) guided the investigation:

RQ1: How do temporal changes in texture and mouthfeel during mastication shape the perception of juiciness in plant-based meat alternatives, and how are these dynamics influenced by formulation variables (protein source, fat type, emulsifier level) in comparison with an animal-based reference?

RQ2: What consumer segments emerge based on temporal sensory perception and preferences for PBMA, and how do temporal sensory drivers of liking and individual characteristics (e.g., oral processing behavior, food neophobia, meat attachment, and PBMA attitudes) differ across these segments?

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Overview of experimental procedures

To address the RQs, we implemented an experimental approach integrating formulation manipulations with multi-level sensory evaluation. We produced plant-based burger patties with systematic variations in fat source and emulsifier concentration, using a beef patty as the reference standard. Sensory characterization employed two complementary approaches: trained panelists performed descriptive sensory analysis focusing on texture profiling with temporal resolution (measurements at 5 and 10 chews), while consumers evaluated overall and modality-specific liking, tracked dynamic texture perception using temporal check-all-that-apply (TCATA), and provided demographic, behavioural and psychographic data for segmentation analysis.

All experiments took place at the sensory laboratory of the University of southern Denmark (SDU) in Odense, Denmark between October and November 2024. Ethical approval for all sensory studies was granted by SDU's Research Ethics Committee prior to conducting the study. All data were collected using the RedJade software (RedJade Sensory Solutions LLC, Pleasant Hill, CA, USA).

The following sections present each methodological component in detail.

2.2. Materials

Texturized protein and plant protein were purchased from ADM (Illinois, USA). Ground beef with 8–12% and 14–18% of fat and rapeseed oil were obtained from a local supermarket (Bilka, Odense, Denmark). Palm olein was purchased from Perdue Agribusiness (Maryland, USA), and palm oil was mimicked by combining palm olein and palm stearin (Wilmar, Singapore) at a ratio of 67:33. Ground beef suet was purchased from a local butcher (Odense, Denmark), mixed with water, and rendered by heating at 85 °C. The melted fat was strained through a fine mesh stainless-steel strainer, then cooled at 5 °C to solidify. After several cycles of melting and solidification for purification, the beef tallow was collected and stored at –18 °C. Experimental emulsifiers were provided by Novonesis. Although all selected fat sources are used in commercial plant-based burgers, their selection was primarily driven by the need to provide contrasts in physicochemical and emulsification functionality, rather than to reflect market

prevalence.

2.3. Sample preparations and serving

In all formulations, fat was incorporated using a pre-formed oil-in-water emulsion to ensure consistent fat dispersion and structural stability. Experimental patties were produced from a standardized base recipe using an incomplete factorial design. Two main factors were varied: fat source (rendered beef tallow, palm oil, rapeseed oil, and palm olein) and emulsifier level (0%, 10%, and 20%). A total of nine samples were generated. For rapeseed oil and palm olein, three emulsifier concentrations were tested, while tallow and palm oil were prepared without added emulsifier. All samples contained 12% fat. Reference samples were prepared using ground beef. Ground beef with 8–12% fat was mixed with ground beef with 14–18% fat in proportions adjusted to obtain a final fat content of approximately 12%. Full sample details are provided in Table 1.

Emulsion preparation. Emulsions were prepared separately using different fat sources with a Proficook 501,188 stand mixer. Salt (0.58%) was dissolved in pre-heated water (58.14%, 50 °C) and transferred to the mixing bowl, followed by pre-heated fat (27.91%, 50 °C), which was incorporated at low speed for 1 min. Plant-based protein (13.37%) was gradually added over 2 min, after which mixing speed was increased to level 3 for 1 min to ensure proper emulsification.

Patty dough preparation. In parallel, texturized plant-based protein (18.00%) was hydrated in cold water (34.00%, 4 °C) and mixed at low speed for 15 min. The freshly prepared emulsion (43.00%) was then combined with the hydrated protein and mixed for 1 min, after which the remaining dry ingredients, isolated protein (1.25%), colorant (0.75%), methylcellulose (1.55%), flavor (0.40%), umami flavor (0.27%), beef flavor (0.32%), and salt (0.45%), were incorporated. The mixture was blended for 2 min to obtain a homogeneous dough. One batch per sample was prepared.

Shaping, cooking, and serving. Patties (40 g; 7 cm diameter, 1 cm height) were shaped using a stainless-steel ring mold and cooked in an air fryer (Foodi 10-in-1 DT200EU, Ninja, England) at 190 °C. Samples were flipped after 90 s and cooked until a core temperature of 58 °C was reached (proximately 4 min). Prior to serving, patties were held in insulated styrofoam boxes at 50 °C, for no longer than 15 min).

For both the descriptive analysis and consumer test, samples were

Table 1

Overview of experimental samples included in the sensory studies. The samples consisted of one animal-based beef patty (ANI) and eight plant-based patties (PBMA). All plant-based patties were formulated with a consistent fat level of 12%, but varied in fat source (vegetable oil or animal fat) and emulsifier level (0%, 10%, or 20%). The table also specifies which samples were included in descriptive analysis (DA) and in the consumer study. The column "Sample code" include sample identifiers used in tables and figures.

Type of sample	Sample code	Sample explanation	Descriptive Analysis	Consumer Study
Reference	ANI	Cow meat and fat	X	X
Experimental 3	P0	Palm olein	X	X
Experimental 4	P10	Palm olein 10% emulsifier	X	
Experimental 5	P20	Palm olein 20% emulsifier	X	
Experimental 2	PAL	Palm oil	X	X
Experimental 6	R0	Rapeseed oil	X	X
Experimental 7	R10	Rapeseed oil 10% emulsifier	X	
Experimental 8	R20	Rapeseed oil 20% emulsifier	X	
Experimental 1	TAL	Plant with cow fat (tallow)	X	X

presented on reusable white plastic (polypropylene) plates (\varnothing 20.5 cm) labeled with random three-digit codes and served at $47\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ ($\pm 2.5\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$). Reusable dark gray plastic (polypropylene) cutlery (17.8–18 cm in length) was provided for cutting and evaluation. In the descriptive analysis, samples were served at five-minute intervals, while in the consumer study the serving interval was three minutes. Presentation order for both tests, followed a randomized complete block design (RCBD) (Lawless & Heymann, 2010). For details on which samples were included in each study, see Table 1. Additional test-specific information can be found in sections 2.4 and 2.5.

2.4. Descriptive analysis

Ten assessors (seven males, three females, mean age = 25 years old ± 4.2), selected based on passing a screening test based on (ISO 8586, 2012), and thereafter availability for the whole training and evaluation period. The descriptive analysis was designed to capture temporal changes in texture and juiciness during mastication through structured evaluation at defined chew points. The panel received ten training sessions of two hours each (20 h in total). The training was divided into two main segments, with five training sessions in each. The first training segment, focused on, general sensory science, food texture theory (mechanical, geometrical, body and surface) using different food as references representing textures in food and chewing techniques with explicit emphasis on mastication-stage-specific evaluation and controlled chewing procedures (Bondu et al., 2022; Bourne, 2002; ISO 11036, 2020; ISO 5492, 2009; Rosenthal & Chen, 2023; Szczesniak, 2002). Further the panel also practiced vocabulary development of texture attributes and intensity ratings on several different commercial PBMA samples (Lawless & Heymann, 2010). The second training segment focused on the experimental samples.

The vocabulary was developed according to standard practice (i.e., panel discussions followed by semantic grouping and matching to references until a consensus list was obtained), and the panel was calibrated during those training sessions. The development of the attributes, references and definition was inspired by literature (ISO 11036, 2020; ISO 5492, 2009; Szczesniak, 2002) and further developed by the panel. The final vocabulary consisted of sixteen different texture, mouthfeel and flavor attributes, where some were evaluated one time and others at different chewing times to provide mastication-stage-specific temporal resolution of sensory perception (*firm*, *malleable*, *fracturability*, *chewy* (5,10 chews), *gummy* (5,10 chews), *denseness*, *granularity* (5,10,15 chews), *fibrous* (5,10 chews), *homogeneity*, *fatty*, *juicy* (5,10 chews), *dryness* (5,10 chews), *mouthcoating* and *mouth dryness*, *umami* (5,10 chews), *overall flavor* (5,10 chews) providing a total of 25 evaluations points per sample. Table 2 provides a detailed overview of the attributes and the reference material used. At each stage, all attributes were assessed before moving to the next chew count, ensuring a consistent temporal evaluation sequence and controlled comparison across mastication stages. See Table 2 for further information on the attributes, definitions, reference materials, etc.

The final assessment was conducted in individual evaluation booths within a sensory laboratory, under controlled environmental conditions, including standardized room temperature, humidity, under clear lighting, in accordance with (ISO 8589, 2010). The sample was served as a three-bite sample. First bite to evaluate the mechanical attributes and flavors, second bite to evaluate the geometrical attributes, and the third bite to evaluate the body and surface attributes, reflecting the progression of texture perception during oral processing.

Samples were evaluated in triplicates using a 15 cm anchored line scale, ranging from “a little” to “a lot.” With respect to anchor labels, two exceptions were made for the attributes *fracturability*, which was evaluated from “a few pieces” to “many pieces,” and *granularity*, evaluated from “small” to “large” particle size.

Palate cleansers included warm water ($60\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$), sparkling water (room temperature), white toast bread (crust removed), and cucumber slices

(without peel or seeds).

2.5. Consumer study

Consumers ($n = 109$, mean age 25 y.o. ± 5.2 , 31% female) were recruited primarily from students and staff at SDU. All participated on a voluntarily basis, and received no financial reimbursement, however snacks were provided after the test (chips, chocolate and fruit). Ethical approval for the experiment was obtained, and all participants signed informed consent forms prior to participation.

Consumers evaluated five of the nine samples (TAL, PAL, ANI, PO, RO), in order to avoid overburdening participants. Emulsifier variations were excluded from the consumer test to keep the TCATA task manageable and avoid cognitive overload, since we considered that subtle formulation differences are better suited for trained panels than for consumer-based temporal profiling. The samples were served in a completely randomized order (Lawless & Heymann, 2010), in identical environmental conditions as the trained panel.

Each sample was presented as a two-bite portion: the first bite was used to respond to the Temporal Check-All-That-Apply (TCATA) questions, and the second bite was used to answer three liking questions (texture, flavor, and overall liking). Samples were prepared and served one at a time, as described in Section 2.2. Room-temperature water was provided in each booth as a palate cleanser.

After the welcoming introduction, a brief training and practice session was included prior to the main TCATA evaluation (“training” is here intended as familiarization with the TCATA procedure, not to be confused with the training provided to the descriptive panel). This approach was based on Jaeger et al. (2017), who showed that familiarization enhances discrimination without significantly altering the temporal profiles. For this study, ten TCATA attributes (*firm*, *crumbly*, *chewy*, *coarse* (*big particles*), *grainy* (*small particles*), *juicy*, *dry*, *fatty/greasy*, *gummy*, *springy*) were selected to represent the most relevant texture and mouthfeel perceptions of the samples (Table 2). These attributes were developed using vocabulary generated by the sensory panel in the descriptive analysis and translated into consumer-friendly words based on literature (Bondu et al., 2022; Szczesniak, 2002). The number of attributes was deemed appropriate for consumers on the basis of Jaeger et al. (2018), who found that TCATA remains effective with up to fifteen terms.

Attributes were presented in a completely randomized order between consumers, but not within consumers (i.e., each consumer was presented with the same attribute order in the TCATA for all five samples). Each evaluation lasted 60 s, during which participants were instructed to report perceptions continuously throughout the entire period. The TCATA task required participants to manually check and uncheck attributes as sensations appeared and disappeared, without automated fading.

After evaluating the five samples, consumers answered a battery of background questions. These of consumer demographics (age, gender, frequency of consumption animal-based meat and plant-based meat), Dietary Habits Questionnaire (De Backer & Hudders, 2015), Mouth Behaviour Questionnaire (MBQ) (Jeltema et al., 2016), Food Neophobia Scale (FNS) (Flight et al., 2003), Meat alternatives Rejection scale (MAR) (Wassmann et al., 2025), and Meat Attachment Questionnaire (MAQ) (Graça et al., 2015). The entire test took approximately 40 min to complete.

2.6. Data analysis

All analyses were conducted in R version 4.3.3 (R Core Team, 2024). Significance was set at $\alpha = 0.05$ and multiplicity was controlled via p -value adjustments when required.

2.6.1. Descriptive analysis

Descriptive sensory data were analyzed using linear mixed-effects

Table 2

Sensory vocabulary developed by the trained panel to describe the samples. Also mentioned are the numbers of chews at evaluation point, references, definition, chewing technique used and the words used in the TCATA. Na = not applicable.

DA attributes	Category	Food reference	Definition	Chewing technique	TCATA attribute
Mechanical – 1st bite					
Firm 1 chew	Hardness	Olive/frankfurter sausage ^a (Not firm: cream cheese) ^a	Force required to achieve a given deformation ^{bc}	Place the solid sample between the molar teeth and chew gently, evaluation the force required to compress the food ^a	Firm
Malleable 1 chew	Springiness	Big marshmallow ^a (Not springy: cream cheese) ^a	Rapidity of recovery from a deformation force ^{bc}	Place the solid sample between the molar teeth and compress it partially. Remove the force and evaluate the degree and rapidity of recovery ^a	Springy
Fracturability 1 chew	Fracturable	Digestive cracker (Not crumbly: soft caramel) little: break into 2 pieces lot: break into many pieces	Force necessary to break a product into crumbs and pieces ^{bc}	Place the solid sample between the molar teeth and bite down evenly until the sample, crumble, cracks or shatters, evaluation the force with which the food moves away from the teeth ^a	Crumbly
Mechanical – Chewing (still 1st bite – now chewing)					
Chewy 5, 10 chews	Cohesiveness, Chewiness ^c	pickled mushroom (Not chewy: ice cream)	Work required/time to masticate a solid product onto the state of swallowing ^{bc}	Chew sample with molar teeth until phase change ^a – require effort to bite through – resistance when chewing	Chewy
Gummy 5, 10 chews	Gumminess	Overcooked oatmeal ^b (Not gummy: kidney beans)	Effort needed to break up the food ready for swallowing ^b	Chew sample with molar teeth until phase change – stretches when bitten – may leave residues on teeth.	Gummy
Flavor Chewing (still 1st bite – now chewing)					
Umami flavor 5, 10 chews	basic taste	Umami 0.49 g/L	Perception of savory, brothy flavor during chewing	Chew and evaluate during mid and late chewing stages	Not used
Overall flavor intensity 5,10 chews	flavor	Overall flavor intensity	Combined intensity of all flavors perceived during chewing	Chew and assess full flavor impression at 5 and 10 chews	Not used
Geometrical – Chewing phase (2nd bite – new sample bite)					
Dense 1 chew	Denseness	Frankfurter sausage	Perception of compactness after biting completely through it ^b	Chew through and evaluate overall solidity	Not used
Granularity 5, 10, 15 chews (lumpy, coarse, grainy)	Granularity	Cottage cheese ^b Oatmeal coarse ^b Oatmeal fine ^b Corn flour- coarse ^b	Textural perception of particle size ^b <i>There might be many different sized, we are looking for the most dominant</i>	Chew and focus on the most dominant grainy or coarse sensation	Coarse (big particles) Grainy (small particles)
Fibrous 5, 10 chews	Conformation	Pineapple (from can)	Perception of particle shape and orientation Long particles oriented on the same direction ^b	Chew and notice if it splits along strands or directions	Not used
Homogeneity/uniformity 5 chews	A combination of denseness, granularity and conformation	Very uniform; <i>Cream cheese, pâté = uniform</i> NOT: <i>Cottage cheese, granola bar</i>	Perception of uniform particle size and structure throughout chewing. Higher homogeneity feels smooth and even; lower homogeneity feels uneven, grainy, or changing in texture ^{bc}	Chew and assess how evenly the texture breaks down. Focus on consistency vs. variation in mouthfeel	Not used
Moisture (3rd bite - last sample bite)					
Juicy 5, 10 chew	Body and Surface	Moisture/fat release	Perception of water released ^a	Notice saliva interaction and moisture sensation	Juicy
Dry 5, 10 chew	Body and Surface	Saliva needed	Perception of water absorbed ^a	Notice saliva interaction and moisture sensation	Dry
Fat (after swallowing)					
Fatty	Body and Surface	lard ^b	Perception of fat within the product ^a – how much fat is in the sample	Was evaluated as the first attribute for the 3rd bite.	Fatty/greasy
Mouthcoating	Body and Surface	na	The sensation of a coating of the mouth	na	Not used
Back/side of tongue coating/dryness	Body and Surface	Sample R0/P0 for nothing and R20/P20 for a lot	The sensation of a coating/dryness of the sides/back on the tongue	Evaluated near the end of sample	Not used

^{a,b,c}Inspired by ^a (ISO 11036, 2020), ^b (ISO 5492, 2009), ^c (Szczesniak, 2002), but finally developed by the panel.

models with Sample as a fixed effect, and Assessor and Replicate as random effects using the 'lmerTest' package (Kuznetsova et al., 2017). Significant differences between samples were identified using Tukey-adjusted pairwise comparisons of estimated marginal means using the package 'multcomp' (Hothorn et al., 2009). Temporal changes in selected texture and flavor attributes across mastication stages (5, 10, and 15 chews) were assessed using paired *t*-tests, both overall and within samples, to evaluate shifts in perception during oral processing.

Principal Component Analysis (PCA) was performed on sensory attribute intensity scores (mean-centred) to examine multivariate relationships between samples and sensory descriptors, using the packages 'FactoMineR' (Lê et al., 2008) for the analysis and 'factoextra' (Kassambara & Mundt, 2016) for visualizations.

2.6.2. Consumer liking

Consumer ratings of overall, texture, and flavor liking were collected on 9-point hedonic scales. Because the data are ordinal, within each sample (ANI, P0, PAL, R0, TAL) differences between consumer clusters were tested using Kruskal–Wallis tests ($\alpha = 0.05$). When the overall test was significant, Dunn's post hoc tests with Holm adjustment were applied. For overall comparisons among samples pooled across consumers, the same Kruskal–Wallis followed by Dunn–Holm procedure was used, and different superscript letters denote significant differences. Distributions were visualized with violin plots (boxplot + jitter overlay) for each sample \times attribute panel, with the panel *p*-value reporting the Kruskal–Wallis result.

2.6.3. Temporal Check-All-That-Apply (TCATA)

TCATA was used to characterize dynamic texture perception across a 60 s mastication period. Ten texture attributes were recorded as binary time series (0 = not cited, 1 = cited) at 0.5 s intervals for each consumer \times sample \times attribute.

For the full consumer panel, citation proportions at each timepoint were computed to obtain normalized citation curves for each attribute and sample. Curves were smoothed with Locally Estimated Scatterplot Smoothing (span = 0.20) for visualization. One-way ANOVAs at each timepoint were used descriptively to indicate timepoints where samples differed. No multiplicity adjustment across timepoints was applied.

To examine inter-individual differences, the same analytical pipeline was applied within each consumer cluster (the process to identify the consumer clusters is explained in Section 2.6.4.). Cluster-wise citation proportions were normalized by cluster size. Within clusters, per-timepoint one-way ANOVAs assessed sample differences. For summary metrics, onset, duration, and offset were computed for each attribute and compared across clusters by ANOVA followed by Tukey's HSD when applicable.

For overview visualizations, a Sample \times Cluster \times Attribute matrix of time-averaged citation proportions (0–60 s) was computed and displayed as a heatmap with rows ordered by cluster then sample (no row clustering) and columns (attributes) hierarchically clustered on z-scored values using Euclidean distance and average linkage.

To enable multivariate analysis, TCATA data were aggregated by computing mean citation proportions across the evaluation period (0–60 s) for each sample and attribute, resulting in a continuous data matrix representing overall attribute dominance. This transformation allows the data to be treated as continuous variables, making them suitable for principal component analysis (PCA, e.g., Castura et al., 2016). PCA (FactoMineR, (Lê et al., 2008)) was performed on the same time-averaged matrix with attributes centred and scaled, and trajectory plots (package 'tempR', (Castura, 2024)) were used to visualize temporal evolution by cluster and sample.

2.6.4. Consumer segmentation

Multiple Factor Analysis (MFA) (Pagès, 2005) was conducted in the 'FactoMineR' package (Lê et al., 2008) to integrate six variable blocks: liking scores (overall, flavor, texture per sample), TCATA temporal

metrics (onset, offset, duration, frequency per sample), demographics (age, gender), psychographics (MAQ, MAR, FNS), dietary profile (frequency of meat and plant-based consumption, dietary status), and mouth-behavior preferences (preferred and non-preferred textures). All blocks were weighted equally at the block level; continuous variables were centred and scaled, and categorical variables were treated as nominal.

Consumer segmentation was obtained using Hierarchical Clustering on Principal Components (HCPC) applied to the MFA individual coordinates. Clustering was carried out in the full MFA factor space, using Euclidean distances and Ward's agglomeration, followed by a *k*-means consolidation step. All fifty-six non-zero MFA dimensions were retained for clustering, accounting for 100 % of the explained variance and ensuring equal representation of sensory response blocks and participant trait blocks in the segmentation. Although including all components can introduce minor noise from low-variance dimensions, this approach preserved subtle yet potentially meaningful variation across data blocks.

For comparison, clustering was also conducted using 10, 15, and 20 principal components based on the scree plot (Appendix A1 in Supplementary material).

Cluster validation (silhouette width, bootstrap stability, and dissolution probabilities) indicated that the two-cluster configuration was slightly more stable numerically (mean silhouette = 0.176 vs 0.157 for three clusters). However, the dendrogram revealed a distinct three-branch structure, and the three-cluster solution achieved higher internal separation and interpretability. Importantly, the variables contributing most to the primary MFA dimension (Appendix A2), dietary profile (including frequency of animal and plant-based meat consumption) and psychographic measures, showed significant differences between clusters for several key indicators ($p < 0.001$; Table 4), confirming that the segmentation reflects distinct positions along the main attitudinal–behavioural gradient identified in the MFA. On this basis and by following established methodological guidance that prioritises interpretability and theoretical coherence over purely numerical optimisation (Dolnicar, 2002; Müller & Hamm, 2014; Wedel & Kamakura, 2000), the three-cluster configuration was retained as the most meaningful representation of consumer heterogeneity in PBMA perception.

This integrated design combines product responses (liking; TCATA-based temporal metrics) with participant descriptors (demographics, psychographics, dietary profile, and self-reported mouth-behavior/texture preferences). The rationale is that cluster structure can arise both from how consumers perceive the samples and from stable individual traits that systematically shape those perceptions; therefore, including both sources yields a more informative segmentation than clustering on liking/TCATA alone, in line with recent work showing that oral processing/bolus characteristics and consumer traits modulate dynamic texture perception and acceptance (e.g., Brouwer et al., 2025; Xue et al., 2025; Zhang et al., 2024).

Differences between clusters were examined for all continuous variables using Kruskal–Wallis test followed by Dunn's post hoc tests with Holm adjustment in case of significant ($\alpha = 0.05$). Categorical variables (e.g., gender, dietary status, texture preferences) were compared using Pearson's chi-squared test, or Fisher's exact test when cell counts were < 5 . For dietary habit categories, differences between clusters were assessed based on the overall distribution of categories using these tests. When the overall test was significant, pairwise comparisons between clusters were conducted, and results are presented using letter groupings for descriptive interpretation. Ordinal frequency-of-consumption variables (animal- and plant-based meat) were coded as ordered numerical categories reflecting decreasing consumption frequency (1 = 5–7 times per week, 2 = 3–4 days per week, 3 = 1–2 days per week, 4 = 1–2 times per month, 5 = 3–4 times per year, 6 = 1–2 times per year, 7 = never) and treated as continuous approximations for comparison across clusters. Corresponding qualitative frequency descriptors and their numerical coding are provided in Table 4 to aid interpretation.

3. Results

3.1. Sensory descriptive analysis

The linear mixed effect model on the descriptive (trained panel) data revealed highly significant ($p < 0.001$) sample effects for all attributes. Mean scores, standard deviations, p -values, and post-hoc comparisons are presented in Table 3. A visual overview of attribute intensity across the mechanical, geometrical, and body and surface texture categories is provided in Appendix B to support the interpretation of Table 3. These data clearly illustrate the higher mechanical strength, flavor intensity, and fat-related mouthfeel of the animal-based sample (ANI), as well as the variation introduced by different plant-based (TAL, PAL, R0, R10, R20, P0, P10, P20, refer to Table 1 for information about the samples) formulations and emulsifier levels.

3.1.1. Multivariate overview of sensory differences

The PCA (Fig. 1) revealed clear sample differentiation, with the first two dimensions respectively explaining 71.1% (Dim 1) and 26.1% (Dim 2) of the total variance, indicating a very strong internal structure in the data. Dim 1 primarily separated samples based on protein source, clearly distinguishing the animal-based sample (ANI) from the plant-based protein variants.

Attributes such as *umami flavor* (chew 5 and 10), *firmness*, *juiciness*, *fattiness*, *fibrousness*, and *denseness* were positively correlated with Dim 1, aligning closely with the positioning of the ANI sample. In contrast, plant-based samples aligned negatively on Dim 1, correlating with attributes such as *fracturability*, *dryness* (chew 5 and 10), and *back-of-tongue coating*.

These patterns correspond to the differences in mean values observed in Table 3, where it can be seen that ANI generally exhibited significantly higher intensity scores for the mechanical attributes: *firmness*, *chewiness*, *gumminess*, and *malleability* across all chewing stages, compared to the plant-based samples. Only *fracturability* showed the opposite result, where the plant-based samples broke into more pieces, indicating a more brittle texture (Table 3 – see also Appendix B for further visualizations of the differences between the samples).

Dim 2 was mainly associated with emulsifier level, separating plant-based samples according to emulsifier concentration. Samples with 20% emulsifier (P20, R20) were associated with higher *granularity* (chews 5, 10 and 15) and *back-of-tongue coating*, while 0% emulsifier samples (TAL, PAL, R0, P0) correlated more strongly with *homogeneity*. This indicates that emulsifier concentration, more than fat source, structured the sensory differences within the plant-based samples.

At the attribute level, this was reflected in differences in *homogeneity*, where higher emulsifier inclusion (10–20%) was associated with lower *homogeneity*, while samples without emulsifier (P0, R0, TAL, PAL) retained higher internal consistency. In addition, ANI exhibited significantly higher values for *fattiness*, *juiciness*, and *mouthcoating*, whereas plant-based samples were characterized by higher *dryness* (Table 3).

The PCA indicates that both protein source and emulsifier level systematically influence sensory properties across the samples. These multivariate patterns highlight the underlying structure of descriptive data. Appendix C provides correlations between the original variables and the PCA dimensions which support the visual interpretations presented here.

3.1.2. Temporal changes across chewing cycles

The temporal differences between chew 5 and 10 (and 15 in *granularity*) further illustrate how texture and flavor attributes evolved during mastication (Fig. 2). *Granularity* increased significantly in most plant-based samples during this interval, particularly in those with higher emulsifier content such as P20 ($p < 0.001$), followed by R20 and P10, indicating accelerated structural fragmentation.

Juiciness declined most sharply in the ANI sample and R10 between chew 5 and 10 ($p < 0.01$), indicating a rapid reduction in perceived

moisture or lubrication during mastication. In contrast, P20 and TAL showed relatively stable *juiciness* over time, suggesting better retention or slower release of moisture. These changes in *juiciness* occurred alongside increases in *granularity* across samples.

Mechanical attributes also reflected these changes. *Chewiness* and *gumminess* declined more markedly in plant-based samples, particularly in P10 and PAL, whereas ANI maintained stable values across the chewing cycle ($p < 0.001$), indicating greater texture resilience. These declines in *chewiness* and *gumminess* coincided with increases in *granularity*, reflecting earlier structural breakdown in plant-based samples.

Notably, TAL and PAL, despite being plant-based and containing no added emulsifier, exhibited a slower progression toward *granularity* and more gradual declines in *flavor* and *moisture* across chewing cycles. In contrast, R0 and P0, which also lacked added emulsifier, fragmented more rapidly and showed steeper increases in *granularity* and *dryness*.

Across samples, decreases in *juiciness* occurred in parallel with increases in *granularity* and *dryness*, indicating that changes in *juiciness* were associated with structural breakdown during mastication. These changes were more pronounced in plant-based samples, particularly those with higher emulsifier levels, compared to ANI.

3.2. Consumer liking

Overall liking results showed that the animal-based sample (ANI) was significantly more liked than all plant-based alternatives ($p < 0.001$), including the plant-based sample containing animal fat (TAL). ANI received the highest mean scores for texture (6.2 ± 1.9), flavor (6.8 ± 1.7), and overall liking (6.6 ± 1.7). No significant differences were found between the plant-based samples across any of the liking dimensions, indicating a relatively uniform level of acceptance within that group. However, inspection of the violin plots (Fig. 3) revealed considerable variation in consumer responses, particularly for the plant-based samples. Interestingly, the ANI ratings tended to be more narrowly distributed and approximately normal, whereas liking for the plant-based patties displayed wider and often bimodal distributions, indicating larger individual differences in perception and acceptance. Relatedly, while ANI was consistently preferred across all liking dimensions, the lack of differentiation among plant-based alternatives may reflect individual variability in consumer expectations or preferences. Such heterogeneity provides a strong rationale for the subsequent cluster analysis which we present later in the paper (Section 3.5.2).

3.3. Temporal texture perception (TCATA)

This section presents the results of the TCATA analysis, which aimed to uncover how texture perception evolved dynamically over the course of mastication across different consumer clusters. Ten texture attributes were evaluated: *chewy*, *coarse (big particles)*, *crumbly*, *dry*, *fatty/greasy*, *firm*, *grainy (small particles)*, *gummy*, *juicy*, and *springiness*. See section 3.5.3 for cluster based differences.

To provide an overview of how texture perception evolved dynamically across the full consumer sample, TCATA citation curves were generated for each of the ten evaluated texture attributes. Fig. 4 presents normalized TCATA citation curves for ten texture attributes across the five samples over the 60-s mastication period. Red dots indicate time-points where significant differences between samples were detected ($p < 0.05$, ANOVA per timepoint). Several attributes showed clear temporal and sample-specific differences.

Firmness was the most discriminating attribute overall, with ANI showing a significantly higher citation proportion than other samples for nearly the entirety of the evaluation period (60 s). *Juicy* also exhibited distinct temporal differences between samples, particularly in the early mastication phase (approximately 7 to 35 s). P0 was most frequently cited as *juicy* during the first 20 s, closely followed by ANI and R0, suggesting a rapid initial moisture release in these samples. However, citation rates for *juiciness* declined for all samples after 30 s, indicating

Table 3

Means and standard deviations (SD) of perceived intensity scores (measured on a 15 cm line scale) for the DA attributes in the nine samples evaluated by the trained panel. By row, mean scores sharing the same letter are not significantly different (Tukey $p < 0.05$). The numbers 1, 5, 10 and 15 after an attribute refers to the number of chews this attribute was evaluated at. The last two attributes (*mouthcoating* and *back of tongue coating*) were evaluated after swallowing the sample.

Attribute (chews)	Sample																			
	p-val	ANI Mean	(SD)	P0 Mean	(SD)	P10 Mean	(SD)	P20 Mean	(SD)	PAL Mean	(SD)	R0 Mean	(SD)	R10 Mean	(SD)	R20 Mean	(SD)	TAL Mean	(SD)	
Mechanical & flavors																				
Firm (1)	<0.001	14.7 ^a	(0.3)	8.6 ^{bc}	(2.9)	5.7 ^{de}	(3.5)	3.5 ^{ef}	(3.3)	9.2 ^b	(2.9)	8.4 ^{bc}	(3.3)	6.4 ^{cd}	(4.0)	2.3 ^f	(3.3)	9.9 ^b	(3.3)	
Malleable (1)	<0.001	13.1 ^a	(4.0)	8.1 ^b	(3.7)	6.8 ^{bc}	(4.4)	4.9 ^c	(4.6)	8.9 ^b	(3.0)	7.4 ^{bc}	(3.4)	7.5 ^{bc}	(4.5)	4.5 ^c	(5.1)	8.6 ^b	(3.7)	
Fracturability (1)	<0.001	0.3 ^e	(0.4)	4.0 ^d	(2.8)	7.1 ^b	(2.9)	13.0 ^a	(2.8)	4.6 ^{cd}	(3.2)	5.5 ^{bcd}	(3.2)	6.7 ^{bc}	(3.7)	13.0 ^a	(2.3)	3.9 ^d	(2.6)	
Chewy (5)	<0.001	14.1 ^a	(1.5)	3.9 ^c	(2.7)	5.2 ^{bc}	(3.5)	7.4 ^b	(3.8)	5.4 ^{bc}	(3.4)	4.4 ^c	(3.3)	5.1 ^{bc}	(3.7)	5.3 ^{bc}	(4.0)	5.5 ^{bc}	(3.0)	
Gummy (5)	<0.001	14.2 ^a	(1.0)	4.6 ^d	(3.4)	6.0 ^{bcd}	(3.3)	8.4 ^b	(3.8)	7.4 ^{bc}	(2.8)	4.8 ^d	(3.9)	5.7 ^{cd}	(3.8)	7.6 ^{bc}	(3.9)	6.0 ^{bcd}	(3.4)	
Umami flavor (5)	<0.001	12.6 ^a	(2.1)	7.8 ^{bc}	(3.5)	6.9 ^b	(3.9)	6.6 ^b	(2.7)	8.1 ^b	(3.4)	7.6 ^b	(3.4)	6.1 ^b	(3.9)	5.9 ^b	(3.7)	8.1 ^b	(3.3)	
Overall flavor intensity (5)	<0.001	10.3 ^a	(3.4)	6.3 ^{bc}	(3.3)	4.3 ^c	(3.1)	5.1 ^{bc}	(2.6)	6.8 ^b	(3.1)	6.0 ^{bc}	(3.1)	4.2 ^c	(3.1)	5.0 ^{bc}	(3.0)	6.6 ^b	(3.4)	
Chewy (10)	<0.001	13.4 ^a	(2.1)	3.2 ^c	(2.7)	5.0 ^{bc}	(3.3)	7.2 ^b	(3.6)	5.3 ^{bc}	(3.2)	3.8 ^c	(3.1)	5.0 ^{bc}	(3.6)	5.4 ^{bc}	(4.2)	4.4 ^c	(2.9)	
Gummy (10)	<0.001	13.7 ^a	(2.0)	4.6 ^d	(3.3)	5.8 ^{bcd}	(3.4)	8.2 ^b	(3.5)	6.7 ^{bcd}	(3.4)	4.6 ^d	(3.9)	5.3 ^{cd}	(3.2)	7.1 ^{bc}	(3.6)	5.6 ^{cd}	(3.3)	
Umami flavor (10)	<0.001	12.4 ^a	(2.3)	7.5 ^b	(3.2)	5.8 ^b	(4.1)	6.9 ^b	(2.6)	7.6 ^b	(3.2)	7.3 ^b	(3.5)	5.7 ^b	(3.6)	6.0 ^b	(3.5)	7.9 ^b	(3.2)	
Overall flavor intensity (10)	<0.001	9.9 ^a	(4.0)	6.3 ^{bc}	(2.8)	3.5 ^e	(2.7)	5.6 ^{bcde}	(2.4)	6.4 ^{bc}	(3.1)	6.0 ^{bcd}	(3.2)	4.0 ^{de}	(3.0)	4.6 ^{cde}	(2.6)	6.9 ^b	(3.4)	
Geometrical																				
Denseness (1)	<0.001	14.0 ^a	(1.4)	8.3 ^b	(3.1)	5.8 ^c	(3.1)	2.4 ^d	(1.9)	9.2 ^b	(2.5)	8.2 ^b	(3.2)	7.3 ^{bc}	(3.2)	2.3 ^d	(2.4)	8.7 ^b	(3.7)	
Granularity (5)	<0.001	13.4 ^a	(2.7)	5.8 ^e	(3.9)	8.6 ^{bcd}	(3.2)	10.8 ^{ab}	(3.5)	7.9 ^{cde}	(3.5)	6.4 ^{de}	(3.9)	7.4 ^{cde}	(3.1)	9.8 ^{bc}	(3.3)	8.2 ^{bcde}	(3.3)	
Fibrous (5)	<0.001	14.5 ^a	(0.6)	5.4 ^b	(3.5)	6.0 ^b	(3.2)	6.8 ^b	(4.0)	6.5 ^b	(3.5)	4.6 ^b	(3.2)	6.2 ^b	(3.1)	6.9 ^b	(4.1)	6.0 ^b	(3.2)	
Granularity (10)	<0.001	12.6 ^a	(3.2)	4.7 ^{de}	(3.2)	7.2 ^{bcd}	(3.4)	9.4 ^b	(3.5)	6.6 ^{cde}	(3.3)	4.2 ^e	(2.5)	6.4 ^{de}	(2.9)	9.0 ^{bc}	(3.2)	6.1 ^{de}	(3.1)	
Fibrous (10)	<0.001	14.0 ^a	(1.3)	4.5 ^{bc}	(3.3)	5.8 ^{bc}	(3.1)	6.6 ^b	(4.0)	5.9 ^b	(3.3)	3.5 ^c	(2.7)	5.3 ^{bc}	(3.09)	6.5 ^b	(4.2)	4.8 ^{bc}	(3.2)	
Homogeneity (10)	<0.001	8.5 ^{ab}	(5.3)	10.8 ^a	(2.4)	7.2 ^{bc}	(3.2)	4.4 ^c	(3.9)	8.3 ^{ab}	(4.1)	9.8 ^{ab}	(3.6)	8.2 ^{ab}	(3.5)	4.4 ^c	(4.0)	8.3 ^{ab}	(3.6)	
Granularity (15)	<0.001	11.0 ^a	(4.0)	3.6 ^{de}	(2.7)	5.9 ^{bcd}	(3.5)	8.0 ^{bc}	(3.8)	5.5 ^{cde}	(3.8)	3.3 ^e	(2.2)	5.1 ^{de}	(3.0)	8.2 ^b	(3.1)	4.5 ^{de}	(3.3)	
Body & Surface																				
Fatty (1)	<0.001	13.6 ^a	(1.9)	8.6 ^b	(2.2)	4.4 ^c	(3.0)	2.2 ^d	(2.6)	7.6 ^b	(3.2)	8.4 ^b	(3.1)	3.5 ^{cd}	(2.4)	2.1 ^d	(1.6)	8.3 ^b	(3.2)	
Juicy (5)	<0.001	14.5 ^a	(0.5)	8.5 ^b	(2.8)	5.1 ^c	(3.5)	2.0 ^d	(2.3)	7.4 ^b	(3.4)	8.0 ^b	(2.7)	4.7 ^c	(2.7)	2.3 ^d	(1.9)	7.3 ^b	(2.6)	
Dry (5)	<0.001	0.8 ^d	(1.6)	5.3 ^c	(3.4)	9.0 ^b	(3.8)	12.4 ^a	(2.1)	6.6 ^c	(4.2)	5.8 ^c	(3.8)	9.3 ^b	(3.3)	12.2 ^a	(2.6)	6.5 ^c	(2.9)	
Juicy 10)	<0.001	13.8 ^a	(1.3)	8.8 ^b	(3.0)	5.1 ^c	(3.6)	2.1 ^d	(2.5)	7.4 ^b	(3.7)	7.9 ^b	(2.8)	4.2 ^{cd}	(2.4)	2.5 ^d	(2.8)	7.2 ^b	(2.6)	
Dry (10)	<0.001	1.4 ^d	(2.4)	5.4 ^c	(3.5)	9.4 ^b	(3.6)	12.6 ^a	(2.3)	6.9 ^c	(4.1)	6.2 ^c	(3.7)	10.4 ^{ab}	(2.6)	12.3 ^a	(3.0)	6.9 ^c	(2.9)	
Mouth coating	<0.001	11.2 ^a	(3.3)	8.1 ^b	(3.2)	7.0 ^b	(3.4)	7.9 ^b	(4.1)	7.6 ^b	(3.2)	7.3 ^b	(3.6)	5.9 ^b	(3.5)	8.1 ^b	(4.2)	8.0 ^b	(2.8)	
Back of tongue coating	<0.001	0.3 ^d	(1.1)	2.7 ^{cd}	(3.4)	4.8 ^{bc}	(4.6)	10.4 ^a	(4.0)	3.5 ^{bc}	(4.5)	3.4 ^{bc}	(3.7)	5.7 ^b	(4.9)	11.9 ^a	(3.5)	2.8 ^{cd}	(3.2)	

Fig. 1. PCA analysis of the samples representing the correlations of the attributes (left) and the samples (right) with the first two principal components. A high cos2 value indicates a good representation of the sample or attribute on the principal component.

Fig. 2. Changes in mean intensity scores (15 cm line scale) for texture and flavor attributes across chews (5–10 chews, unless otherwise stated). * $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$, *** $p < 0.001$.

that sustained *juiciness* was limited, especially in PAL and TAL, which showed consistently low citation rates throughout. Post-hoc comparisons confirmed a significant difference between samples, with P0 perceived more juicy than PAL, while the remaining samples occupied intermediate positions without clear separation. This difference was only evident at specific timepoints, as shown with red in Fig. 4.

Coarse (big particles) displayed multiple significant time segments, including the first 0–10 s, a brief window around 20–22 s, and again at 50–55 s, with varying sample-specific peaks during each phase. *Grainy (small particles)* and *crumbly* also contributed meaningfully to sample discrimination, particularly between 10 and 40 s, with PAL and R0 exhibiting higher citation rates during mid-mastication.

Fatty/greasy, though cited less frequently overall, showed intermittent peaks between 15 and 25 s for select samples such as R0 and TAL, indicating transient perception of lubrication or fat-like coating in some formulations.

In the final few seconds of the evaluation, *chewy* also showed significant differences between samples. *Gummy* and *springiness* remained low across samples and time, indicating limited relevance to product discrimination in this dataset. These findings illustrate the evolution of texture perception over time and identify attributes that contributed most strongly to temporal differentiation between samples.

3.4. Comparison between descriptive analysis (trained panel) and TCATA (consumers)

Fig. 5 compares sample positioning and attribute vectors from Principal Component Analysis (PCA) of the DA (left) and TCATA (right) datasets. For direct comparison, only the five samples assessed in both methods (ANI, TAL, PAL, P0, R0) are shown (see Fig. 1 for the full DA PCA). Variance explained was 89.2% by PC1 and 9.6% by PC2 in DA, versus 45.9% by PC1 and 27.4% by PC2 in TCATA, indicating a stronger

Fig. 3. Violin plots showing overall, texture, and flavor liking scores for each sample across all consumers ($n = 109$). Kruskal–Wallis p -values indicate overall differences between samples for each attribute. Different letters denote significant pairwise differences based on Dunn’s test with Holm adjustment ($p < 0.05$).

Fig. 4. Normalized TCATA citation curves for ten texture attributes across five samples over a 60-s mastication period (all consumers). Each row represents a sample, and each column an attribute. Red dots indicate individual timepoints where significant differences between samples were found (ANOVA per timepoint, $p < 0.05$).

Fig. 5. Principal component maps for texture from (A) Descriptive Analysis (DA; blue) and (B) TCATA (red). Each panel is a separate PCA (scaled variables) computed on the five samples common to both methods (ANI, TAL, PAL, P0, R0). Points are sample scores on PC1–PC2; arrows are attribute loadings (direction/strength). Axis labels show variance explained (DA: PC1 = 89.2%, PC2 = 9.6%; TCATA: PC1 = 45.9%, PC2 = 27.4%), highlighting the stronger PC1 dominance in DA and the broader two-dimensional spread in TCATA. The full DA PCA including all nine samples is shown in Fig. 1. In that analysis, attributes at different chewing stages were included as separate variables, whereas in the present comparison, DA attributes were aggregated across chewing stages to allow alignment with the time-averaged TCATA data.

single-axis structure in DA and a broader two-dimensional spread in TCATA, suggesting that the TCATA data capture a more multidimensional representation of texture perception compared to the more compressed structure observed in the descriptive analysis.

Note that for the TCATA PCA, attributes represent time-averaged citation proportions over the full evaluation period (0–60 s), as opposed to discrete chewing stages in the descriptive analysis.

In the DA PCA, PC1 separated ANI from the plant-based samples. Vectors for *dryness* and *fracturability* were oriented toward the PB samples, whereas most other attributes were associated with ANI. Along PC2, PAL and TAL plotted nearer the directions of *dryness* and *granularity*, while P0 was positioned nearer *homogeneity*. R0 sat between these PB positions on PC2 while remaining separated from ANI on PC1.

In the TCATA PCA, variance was more evenly distributed across PC1–PC2. PC1 primarily separated ANI from P0 and, to a lesser extent, TAL. Along this axis, attributes located nearer ANI included *grainy (small particles)*, *firm*, *crumbly*, and *fatty/greasy*, whereas attributes nearer the P0, TAL and R0 side were *chewy*, *springiness*, and *gummy*. PC2 distinguished PAL from ANI and P0, reflecting a contrast between *dry* and *juicy*: PAL associated with *dry*, while ANI and P0 associated with *juicy*. These results indicate that sample separation in the TCATA PCA was primarily associated with differences in *juicy* and particle-related attributes across samples.

Across both analyses, ANI was positioned apart from the plant-based alternatives, and attribute orientations differed by method. The two sample configurations were broadly concordant (Procrustes correlation $t_0 = 0.84$; $p = 0.058$).

3.5. Consumer characteristics and cluster profiles

Most participants ($n = 109$) identified as omnivores (75.2%), with 24.8% identifying as flexitarians (Table 4). Participants reported consuming animal-based meat (e.g., pork, beef, chicken) on average 5–7 times per week (mean = 1.4, SD = 1.0), while plant-based (PB) meat alternatives were consumed less frequently, averaging 3–4 times per

year (mean = 5.2, SD = 1.5).

Mouth behavior preferences were diverse: 48.6% preferred “chew” textures, 44.0% preferred “crunch,” and 7.3% preferred “smoosh.” None indicated a preference for “suck” textures. When asked about disliked textures, 43.1% selected “suck,” followed by “smoosh” (7.3%), “crunch” (2.8%), and “chew” (0.9%). Nearly half (45.9%) reported no texture aversions.

The mean Food Neophobia Score was 29.8 (SD = 6.2), with 17.4% classified as high neophobia, 50.5% medium, and 32.1% low. The Meat Alternatives Rejection (MAR) score averaged 2.8 (SD = 0.9), and the Meat Attachment Questionnaire (MAQ) score averaged 3.8 (SD = 0.7), indicating moderate openness to alternatives and strong emotional ties to meat.

These results indicate that consumer segments differed in their sensitivity to the temporal evolution of *juiciness*, *dryness*, and structural breakdown during mastication.

3.5.1. Consumer cluster specific differences

Using MFA, participants were segmented into three clusters based on demographic, psychographic profiles, consumption patterns, liking scores, TCATA responses, and mouth behavior (Table 4). All variable blocks were equally weighted. The clustering was based on the full MFA factor space, with all fifty-six non-zero dimensions retained, representing 100% of the explained variance. MFA group contribution plots in Appendix A show that Dimension 1 is mainly associated with dietary profile, psychographics, and mouth behavior variables, while liking and TCATA contribute more strongly to higher-order dimensions. Detailed MFA and hierarchical clustering outputs that support this segmentation are included in Appendix A for reference. These blocks jointly defined the main consumer gradient, from omnivores with high meat attachment and low PBMA familiarity (Clusters 1 and 2) to flexitarians with greater PBMA openness and lower meat attachment (Cluster 3). This combined influence of dietary and attitudinal factors underpins the observed three-cluster structure and aligns with the behavioural differences summarized below.

Table 4

Consumer characteristics overall and by cluster ($n = 109$). Clusters are from the MFA–HCPC segmentation (Section 2.6.4). Categorical variables are shown as n (%); continuous variables as mean (SD). P -values are from overall tests across clusters: one-way ANOVA for continuous variables and Pearson's χ^2 test (or Fisher's exact test when counts <5) for categorical variables. Superscript letters denote significant differences ($p < 0.05$) between clusters following post-hoc pairwise comparisons using Tukey for continuous variables pairwise comparisons of cluster proportions for categorical variables. For categorical variables, p -values represent tests of differences in the overall distribution of categories across clusters, and superscript letters are provided for descriptive interpretation of pairwise differences within each category. Frequency-of-consumption variables were coded as ordinal numerical categories (1 = highest frequency, 7 = never).

Consumer characteristics	Overall $n = 109$ (100%)	Cluster 1 $n = 45$ (41%)	Cluster 2 $n = 39$ (36%)	Cluster 3 $n = 25$ (23%)	P-value (between clusters)
Gender (%)					0.032
Male	68.8	77.8 ^a	71.8 ^{ab}	48.0 ^b	
Female	31.2	22.2 ^a	28.2 ^{ab}	52.0 ^b	
Age					
mean (std)	24.8 (5.3)	24.0 (2.69)	24.2 (4.6)	27.2 (8.4)	0.093
Frequency consumption of animal meat (pork, Cow, chicken etc) (%)					<0.001
mean (std)	1.4 (1.0)	1.1 (0.3) ^b	1.3 (0.5) ^b	2.2 (1.7) ^a	
Average corresponds to	5–7 times a week	5–7 times a week	5–7 times a week	3–4 times a week	
Frequency consumption of PB meat (cow, Chicken, pork, Burger, sausages etc.) (%)					<0.001
mean (std)	5.2 (1.5)	6.1 (1.1) ^a	5.2 (1.1) ^b	3.6 (1.1) ^c	
Average corresponds to	3–4 times a year	1–2 times a year	3–4 times a year	1–2 times a month	
Dietary Status (%)					<0.001
Omnivore	75.2	93.3 ^a	92.3 ^a	16.0 ^b	
Flexitarian	24.8	6.7 ^a	7.7 ^a	84.0 ^b	
Mouth Behavior – Texture preference (%)					
Chew	48.6	60.0 ^a	59.0 ^a	12.0 ^b	<0.001
Crunch	44.0	37.8 ^a	30.8 ^a	76.0 ^b	<0.001
Smooosh	7.3	2.2	10.3	12.0	0.201
Suck	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	NA
Mouth Behavior - Not preferred texture (%)					
Chew	0.9	0.0	2.6	0.0	0.059
Crunch	2.8	6.7	0.0	0.0	0.247
Smooosh	7.3	0.0 ^a	20.5 ^b	0.0 ^a	<0.001
Suck	43.1	35.6	41.0	60.0	0.142
None	45.9	57.8	35.9	40.0	0.106
Food Neophobia (%)					
Mean (std)	29.8 (6.2)	29.1 (6.42)	30.6 (5.83)	29.7 (6.27)	0.549
High	17.4	17.8	23.1	8.0	0.336
Medium	50.5	40.0	53.8	64.0	0.150
Low	32.1	42.2	23.1	28.0	0.170
Meat Alternatives Rejection (MAR)					<0.001
(Mean, std)	2.8 (0.9)	3.4 (0.8) ^a	2.4 (0.8) ^b	2.3 (0.5) ^b	
Meat Attachment Questionnaire (MAQ)					<0.001
(Mean, std)	3.8 (0.7)	4.3 (0.4) ^a	3.8 (0.5) ^b	3.0 (0.7) ^c	

Gender distribution differed significantly between clusters. Clusters 1 and 2 were predominantly male (77.8% and 71.8%, respectively), whereas Cluster 3 had a more balanced gender composition, with 52.0% females. Age did not differ significantly, although Cluster 3 tended to be slightly older (27.2 years) than Clusters 1 and 2 (24.1 and 23.8 years, respectively).

Clear differences emerged in dietary profiles: Clusters 1 and 2 were mostly omnivores, while Cluster 3 included a high proportion of flexitarians (Table 4). Animal meat consumption also varied significantly across clusters. Cluster 3 consumed meat least frequently (approximately 3–4 times per week), followed by Cluster 2 and Cluster 1, both eating animal meat close to on a daily basis. In contrast, plant-based meat consumption varied significantly across all clusters, being lowest in Cluster 1 (1–2 times per year), intermediate in Cluster 2 (approximately 1–2 times per month), and highest in Cluster 3 (around once per week).

In terms of mouth behavior preferences, significant differences were observed for both preferred and non-preferred textures. Cluster 3 showed a higher preference for crunch and lower preference for chew compared with Clusters 1 and 2. They also reported higher dislike for smooosh and suck textures. Cluster 3 further differed from Clusters 1 and 2 by showing more positive attitudes toward plant-based meat alternatives (lower MAR score) and lower meat consumption frequency.

Food neophobia scores did not differ across clusters. Conversely, strong differences were seen in attitudinal scores. Cluster 1 had the highest Meat Alternatives Rejection (MAR) score and the strongest Meat Attachment (MAQ) score, while Cluster 3 had the lowest MAR and a

moderate MAQ. MAQ scores differed significantly between all three clusters. (Table 4).

3.5.2. Differences in liking among clusters

Liking scores for the five samples were analyzed across the three consumer clusters for overall, texture, and flavor liking.

As shown in Fig. 6, significant differences in liking were observed between clusters for nearly all samples and sensory attributes (Kruskal–Wallis, $p < 0.001$ for most comparisons). Dunn–Holm post-hoc tests revealed that Cluster 2 consistently gave higher ratings, particularly for P0, PAL, R0, and TAL. For ANI, clusters also differed significantly (overall $p = 0.0018$; texture $p = 0.00043$; flavor $p = 0.011$), though the pattern was less pronounced, with both Clusters 1 and 2 giving higher ratings than Cluster 3.

Cluster 1 gave the lowest ratings overall, particularly for PAL and TAL, while Cluster 3 showed intermediate scores but often aligned more closely with Cluster 2. Compact-letter displays in Fig. 6 indicate Dunn–Holm groupings: for most samples and attributes, Cluster 2 belonged to group “a,” Cluster 1 to “b,” and Cluster 3 fell between them or shared grouping depending on the sample.

Within-cluster comparisons (see Appendix D for further visualizations) showed clear patterns. Cluster 1 showed the strongest discrimination between samples, consistently distinguishing ANI from the plant-based samples across liking measures. Cluster 2 also differentiated between samples, though to a lesser extent, while Cluster 3 showed no significant within-cluster differences, indicating more uniform liking across samples.

Fig. 6. Violin plots showing overall, flavor, and texture liking scores for each sample by consumer cluster. Kruskal–Wallis p -values indicate overall differences between clusters for each sample and attribute. Different letters denote significant differences based on Dunn test with Holm adjustment ($p < 0.05$).

3.5.3. Differences in TCATA responses among clusters

Analyses assessed both within-cluster differences (how different

samples were perceived within each consumer group) and between-cluster differences (how the same sample was perceived across

Fig. 7. PCA trajectories of TCATA attribute citations by cluster (dimensions 1 and 2). Each plot shows the temporal evolution of texture attribute citations for different samples based on PCA of TCATA data from the three consumer clusters. Colored curves represent the citation trajectories of individual samples over time. Trajectories begin at early time points and progress toward later ones, with sample codes marking their endpoints. Attribute labels indicate their influence on the sensory space defined by the first two principal components, which explain the largest proportion of variance in the data.

groups). In this subsection we report the within-cluster temporal patterns from TCATA, using PCA trajectory maps (Fig. 7) and mean attribute-citation profiles (Fig. 8). Additional detail for PC3-PC4 and cluster-specific biplots are provided in Appendices E–F. Time-resolved between-cluster comparisons (same sample compared across clusters) are given in Appendix G.

Fig. 7 presents PCA trajectories of TCATA attribute citations, comparing how the three consumer clusters perceived each sample over time in a low-dimensional sensory space. Each panel shows one cluster; colored curves trace the temporal path of each sample on the first two principal components, with attribute vectors indicating the directions that structure the space.

In Cluster 1, trajectories formed tighter arcs, particularly for P0, with earlier positioning toward *dry* and *crumbly* attributes during mastication. Cluster 2 showed substantial overlap between most samples trajectories, indicating less pronounced separation between samples, though PAL and R0 gradually separated along the juicy/dry dimension. By contrast, Cluster 3 displayed broader dispersion and more dynamic paths, with samples diverging strongly over time and *juicy* sustained longer before shifting toward *grainy* or *coarse*. These differences indicate variation in how clusters respond to temporal changes in *juicy* and particle-related attributes during mastication. Further, in Cluster 3, the temporal positioning of the tallow sample more closely resembled the plant-based samples, contrasting with Clusters 1 and 2 where tallow was consistently located near the animal-based reference (Fig. 7; Appendix F). This indicates a different perceptual relationship among samples for this segment. Additional details are provided in Appendix E (PCA trajectories for dimensions 3 and 4) and Appendix F (PCA biplots by consumer cluster).

While the PCA trajectories in Fig. 7 illustrated how texture perception evolved over time, Fig. 8 provides the mean citation frequency of each texture attribute for every Sample \times Cluster combination. Each row corresponds to a consumer cluster's perception of a specific sample, and each colour-coded cell reflects the frequency with which a given texture attribute was cited.

Hierarchical clustering was applied to both rows and columns to highlight broader patterns in attribute usage. Cluster 1 showed elevated

use of *crumbly*, *coarse* (*big particles*), and *chewy*, particularly for samples PAL and R0. This aligns with earlier TCATA and PCA results suggesting greater sensitivity to breakdown and fragmentation and is consistent with the chewer-dominant oral profile previously identified for this cluster. Cluster 2 did not exhibit a clear dominant attribute pattern across samples, although some sample-specific differences were observed for *juicy*, particularly for TAL and ANI (Appendix G). Cluster 3 showed fewer pronounced citation peaks across attributes, despite exhibiting broader temporal dispersion in the PCA trajectories (Fig. 7). Notably, *crumbly* was consistently among the most frequently cited attributes for ANI across all three clusters, despite ANI receiving the lowest fracturability scores in the trained-panel evaluation. This discrepancy may indicate that consumers interpreted *crumbly* differently from the trained-panel definition of fracturability, potentially reflecting particle formation during mastication rather than resistance to initial fracture. This is supported by the temporal profile of the *crumbly* attribute in TCATA where the onset of this attribute is typically not at first bite but after 10–120 seconds (Fig. 4), as well as by the correspondence of this attribute *crumbly* with the DA attribute *granularity* (Fig. 5).

For completeness, the full time-resolved TCATA citation curves by cluster, Appendix G, compare how different consumer clusters perceived the same sample across time and texture attributes. Each panel corresponds to one attribute within a given sample, and the three curves reflect the citation trajectories of the three consumer clusters. Time-specific between-cluster differences were observed across samples, particularly for *juicy* and *firm* during early and mid-mastication, and for particle-related attributes during mid mastication. Differences in *juicy* were evident across clusters for several samples, with variation in both the timing and duration of *juicy* perception. Similarly, differences in *firm* were observed primarily during early mastication stages. Particle-related attributes (*crumbly* and *grainy* (*small particles*)) showed differences across clusters, particularly during mid-mastication (10–35 s), indicating variation in perceived fragmentation. In contrast, attributes such as *springiness* and *gummy* showed overlapping citation patterns across clusters, with no significant differences, suggesting a more stable or shared interpretation. The animal-based sample ANI also displayed relatively consistent perception across clusters, indicating that

Fig. 8. Heatmap showing mean citation proportion (0–1) for each TCATA attribute across all Sample \times Cluster combinations, averaged across time points and consumers within each cluster. Each row corresponds to one sample as described by a specific cluster (e.g., 1_P0 = Cluster 1 for sample P0). Reddish colors indicate more frequent citation. Rows are ordered by cluster and sample (no row clustering); columns are hierarchically clustered to reveal patterns in attribute usage across clusters and samples.

variability was more pronounced for the plant-based products.

4. Discussion

4.1. Temporal mechanisms underlying perception of juiciness in plant-based and animal-based burgers (RQ1)

Juiciness perception is increasingly recognised as a dynamic sensory experience that unfolds during mastication rather than as a static attribute perceived at first bite (Szczesniak, 2002; Zhang et al., 2025). Accordingly, the present study examined how temporal changes in texture and mouthfeel during mastication shape juiciness perception in plant-based meat alternatives, and how these dynamics are influenced by formulation variables and comparison with an animal-based reference (RQ1). Previous sensory evaluations of plant-based meat alternatives have frequently relied on static end-point measurements (Castura et al., 2016; Varela & Ares, 2012), which provide limited insight into how structural breakdown and lubrication processes develop during mastication. By combining chew-point descriptive analysis with consumer-based TCATA, the present results therefore offer new insight into how formulation factors shape the temporal interplay between texture disintegration and lubrication processes underlying perceived juiciness. A comparison of the multivariate structures of the DA and TCATA datasets further supports this, as the TCATA data exhibited a more distributed variance across principal components compared to the more compressed structure observed in the descriptive analysis, indicating a more multidimensional representation of texture perception. This suggests that temporal consumer-based methods capture additional aspects of sensory experience that may not be fully captured by static or chew-point-based descriptive approaches, highlighting the importance of incorporating temporal dynamics when evaluating juiciness and texture in plant-based meat alternatives.

Across plant-based patties, emulsifier level emerged as a key modulator of temporal texture perception. In the chew-point-resolved descriptive analysis, higher emulsifier concentrations were associated with reduced *firmness*, *chewiness*, and *malleability*, alongside increased *fracturability*, indicating reduced structural resistance and earlier fragmentation during mastication. As chewing progressed, decreases in *fibrousness* and increases in *granularity* were observed, reflecting the progressive particle comminution and bolus structuring processes that Chen (2009) describes as fundamental stages of oral processing. Importantly, these sensory mechanical changes formed part of a broader temporal breakdown trajectory, in which plant-based patties disintegrated more rapidly and generated granular particle sensations earlier than the animal-based reference. Such accelerated breakdown is consistent with previous work showing that plant-based matrices often lack the hierarchical organization and viscoelastic coherence of muscle tissue, leading to earlier fragmentation during oral processing (Forster et al., 2024; Gao et al., 2025; Shewan et al., 2020).

These structural differences were reflected in the temporal perception of *juiciness*. In both palm- and rapeseed-based patties, increasing emulsifier concentration was associated, in the descriptive analysis, with less sustained *juiciness* and an earlier onset of *dryness* during mastication. Notably, the emergence of *dryness* coincided with increasing *fracturability* and *granularity*, indicating that *dryness* developed alongside mechanical weakening and particle formation rather than as an isolated sensory attribute. This temporal co-occurrence may reflect a progressive loss of lubrication as structural integrity declined during chewing, consistent with saliva-mediated lubrication mechanisms in which food-saliva interactions regulate particle clustering, bolus cohesion, and frictional conditions at oral surfaces (Mosca & Chen, 2017). Although emulsification is commonly intended to improve moisture retention, the present findings suggest that excessive emulsifier levels may over-stabilize the fat-water system, limiting the timely release of fluid required for oral lubrication. Rather than enhancing *juiciness*, excessive stabilization may therefore delay fluid availability at perceptually

critical chewing stages. This interpretation aligns with conceptual frameworks emphasizing that perceived *juiciness* depends less on total moisture content than on the mobility and release of water and lipids at perceptually relevant stages of mastication (McClements, 2024). The role of methylcellulose further supports this interpretation. Rudge et al. (2025) demonstrated that when methylcellulose is added as a powder at relatively high levels, liquid expression and perceived *juiciness* can be reduced due to strong water binding and restricted fluid release. In the present study, the temporal sensory profiles of high emulsifier (20%) formulations suggest that increasing emulsifier concentration may have further enhanced fluid retention within the product matrix. This may have contributed to a more cohesive structure, thereby reducing the efficiency of aqueous and lipid phase release during chewing.

From a sensory perspective, this mismatch between matrix breakdown and fluid availability manifests as earlier *dryness* and reduced lubrication related mouthfeel, often accompanied by earlier emergence of *coarse* and *crumbly* sensations in the consumer TCATA profiles, rather than as a lack of moisture per se. Relatedly, comparisons with the animal-based reference underscored the importance of sustained lubrication for *juiciness* perception. Consistent with descriptive analysis results, the animal-based patty was significantly higher in perceived *juiciness* and *fattiness* than all plant-based samples across chewing stages. It also retained higher *firmness* and *chewiness* over time, delaying the appearance of *granularity*, *coarse*, and *crumbly* perceptions that characterized several plant-based samples. This temporal stability is consistent with the natural muscle fiber architecture and heterogeneous fat distribution in meat, which support gradual breakdown and continuous moisture release during oral processing (Forster et al., 2024; Zhang et al., 2025). In contrast, TCATA results showed that plant-based patties exhibited a temporally compressed breakdown sequence, with *firmness* perceptions declining earlier and *coarse* and *grainy* particle sensations emerging sooner, resulting in a shorter perceptual window of *juiciness* during mastication. These observations suggest that sustained *juiciness* depends not only on moisture availability but on maintaining structural coherence long enough to support progressive lubrication during mastication.

Taken together, these findings demonstrate that formulation strategies such as emulsifier level and fat system influence *juiciness* primarily through their effects on temporal lubrication dynamics rather than static texture attributes. However, *juiciness* changes occurred in parallel with shifts in *firmness*, *chewiness*, *fibrousness*, *fracturability*, *granularity*, and particle-related attributes (*coarse*, *grainy*, *crumbly*), indicating that dynamic texture perception reflects coordinated evolution of multiple mechanical and geometrical cues during mastication. By demonstrating how the persistence of *juiciness* is temporally coupled with structural fragmentation and particle perception, the present results extend current conceptual understanding of texture as a dynamic oral experience rather than a static material attribute (Chen, 2026). Previous studies have mainly characterized juiciness deficits in plant-based burgers using static sensory or oral processing measures (Forster et al., 2024; Ilic et al., 2025), or have proposed lubrication-based conceptual explanations (McClements, 2024; Mosca & Chen, 2017). The present findings extend this understanding by providing time-resolved sensory evidence that the sensory gap between plant-based and meat patties is also expressed in the temporal persistence of lubrication-related sensations during mastication.

4.2. Consumer heterogeneity in temporal texture and juiciness perception and its implications for acceptance (RQ2)

Consumer acceptance of plant-based patties is shaped not only by product-level sensory performance but also by individual differences in sensitivity to the temporal evolution of *juiciness* and structural breakdown during mastication. Differential responses across consumer segments were examined to understand how temporal sensory perception and drivers of liking vary across individuals with different behavioural

and attitudinal profiles (RQ2). These differences include variation in responses to changes in *firmness*, *chewiness*, *fibrousness*, *fracturability*, *granularity*, and particle-related sensations (*coarse*, *grainy*, *crumbly*) across chewing stages. Building on the temporal sensory mechanisms identified in RQ1, particularly differences in the timing of juiciness decline, onset of dryness, and progression of structural breakdown, the consumer segmentation was used as an interpretive framework to examine how these dynamic sensory cues were experienced and evaluated across individuals with differing behavioural and attitudinal profiles. Rather than being defined solely by sensory perception, the resulting consumer segments reflected integrated differences in liking responses, dietary habits, mouth-behavior preferences, and psychographic characteristics. Linking these broader consumer profiles to the temporal sensory patterns observed during mastication provides insight into how differences in oral breakdown perception may contribute to heterogeneous acceptance outcomes. This interpretation aligns with emerging evidence suggesting that juiciness perception is influenced by transient lubrication events during chewing rather than by static product properties alone (Galler & Varela, 2024; Zhang et al., 2024).

Consumer segmentation, based on integrated liking, TCATA, and questionnaire data, identified three groups that differed in their evaluation of the products. One group showed high sensitivity to early-onset *dryness* and rapid fragmentation, resulting in consistently low liking for plant-based burgers and a strong preference for the animal-based reference. For this group, early increases in *fracturability*, *granularity*, and *crumbly* sensations appeared particularly detrimental, especially when accompanied by declining *firmness* and *chewiness*. This pattern aligns with findings that consumers with strong meat attachment are particularly attuned to deviations from meat-like temporal texture trajectories and are less tolerant of early breakdown and lubrication loss (Götze & Brunner, 2021; Kim & Vickers, 2020). In the context of the present study, this group appeared to penalize plant-based patties precisely at the mastication stages where *juiciness* declined most rapidly, consistent with the temporal profiles identified in RQ1.

A second group exhibited more moderate and variable responses to temporal texture changes. Although demographically and behaviorally similar to the first group in terms of meat consumption and PBMA familiarity, their liking responses diverged substantially. This divergence suggests that perceptual sensitivity to temporal texture cues, rather than dietary habits alone, plays a decisive role in acceptance. These consumers appeared less reactive to early *juiciness* loss and more accepting of transient *dryness*, as well as more tolerant of increasing *granularity* and *coarse* particle perception during later chewing stages, supporting the notion that consumer heterogeneity in PBMA acceptance cannot be explained solely by static preferences or consumption frequency (Brouwer et al., 2025).

The third group, composed predominantly of flexitarians with low rejection of plant-based products, demonstrated greater tolerance toward dynamic texture changes, including earlier disintegration and *granularity*. This group appeared less sensitive to reductions in *firmness* and *chewiness* and more accepting of *grainy* and *coarse* sensations, provided that the overall eating experience remained coherent. Importantly, this tolerance did not necessarily translate into uniformly high liking, indicating that openness alone is insufficient to guarantee acceptance. Rather, this group appeared to value a temporally coherent eating experience, even if it did not fully replicate meat-like texture. This observation aligns with expectation-based accounts suggesting that consumers with more flexible sensory expectations are less reliant on strict meat equivalence and more responsive to whether temporal mouthfeel remains broadly satisfying during mastication (Götze & Brunner, 2021).

Segment differences in liking were more closely associated with responses to the temporal evolution of texture attributes during mastication, particularly *juiciness* persistence, *dryness* onset, and structural breakdown, than with static intensity ratings alone. Early decreases in *firmness* and *chewiness* and rapid increases in *fracturability*, *granularity*,

and *crumbly* sensations emerged as critical negative drivers for some consumers but were tolerated or discounted by others. These findings are consistent with Zhang et al. (2024), who demonstrated that *juiciness* perception is dominated by serum release early during mastication and that interindividual differences in sensitivity to this release strongly influence acceptance. By capturing when *juiciness* is gained or lost, and how it co-evolves with *firmness* and particle perception, the temporal sensory approach employed here provides a mechanistic explanation for why products that appear similar under static evaluation can elicit markedly different responses across consumers.

Individual characteristics further modulated sensitivity to temporal texture cues. High meat attachment and PBMA rejection were associated with greater sensitivity to early *dryness* and breakdown, reinforcing their role as barriers to acceptance highlighted in the literature (e.g., Kim & Vickers, 2020). Oral processing behavior also played a role, as consumers preferring a chewing-dominant style were less accepting of rapid disintegration, while those characterized as “crunchers” showed greater tolerance toward particle formation and breakdown, consistent with evidence that oral processing strategies shape dynamic texture perception and liking (Appiani et al., 2023; Ditschun et al., 2025).

Taken together, the results indicate that consumer segments differed primarily in their sensitivity to the timing of juiciness loss and structural breakdown during mastication rather than in their responses to overall texture intensity. Early onset of dryness and rapid particle formation emerged as key rejection points for some consumers, whereas others tolerated these changes provided that the temporal eating experience remained coherent. These findings suggest that improving acceptance of plant-based patties may require tailoring the temporal breakdown profile of products to different consumer groups. For example, products targeting meat-attached consumers (like those in Cluster 1 in this study) may need to sustain firmness and lubrication into later chewing stages, while products aimed at more flexitarian consumers may benefit more from enhancing early juiciness release and limiting mid-mastication dryness. This study therefore highlights temporal texture optimisation as a critical, and currently under-utilised, strategy for closing the sensory gap between plant-based and meat burgerinstead depends on the alignment between product-specific temporal texture trajectories and consumer-specific perceptual expectations and attitudes during mastication, highlighting the importance of integrating dynamic sensory evaluation with consumer heterogeneity when designing next-generation plant-based meat alternatives.

4.3. Limitations and recommendations for future research

This study has several limitations that should be acknowledged. A very important one is that patties were evaluated on their own under controlled conditions, whereas real-world consumption typically occurs in multi-component dishes such as burgers with buns, condiments, and sides. These additional components can interact with the patty, masking or amplifying textural differences and altering mouthfeel and juiciness perception over time during mastication (Varela et al., 2022). Such components may modify oral lubrication, saliva–food interactions, and bolus formation, thereby influencing the temporal evolution of texture and juiciness. Future studies should therefore examine plant-based patties using temporal sensory evaluation in more realistic gastronomic contexts to better predict dynamic consumer experience.

Second, although both fat source and emulsifier level were examined as formulation variables, emulsifier variation was included only in the descriptive sensory analysis and not in the consumer study. This limits the ability to determine how emulsifier-driven temporal textural changes translate into consumer perception and acceptance. Future research could therefore include emulsifier variation in both trained panel and consumer based temporal testing, and explore a broader range of emulsifier types, concentrations, and physicochemical mechanisms to clarify their sensory and hedonic relevance across different fat systems.

Third, differences across fat systems indicate that fat source (and its

interaction with the protein-based matrix with emulsified fat) helps determine juiciness and dryness during mastication, yet the mechanisms remain unclear. Future work should systematically vary fat type and emulsification (including non-emulsified controls) and couple sensory data with targeted physical readouts (instrumental texture, cooking loss, rheology, droplet size, and microstructural imaging). Integrating these measures will clarify how matrix organization, fat distribution, and interfacial behavior translate into perceived juiciness and breakdown.

Finally, consumer segmentation was based on a relatively small and homogeneous sample, which limits generalizability. The three clusters identified in this study, while interpretable and inherently coherent, should therefore best be considered as exploratory. Replication with larger and more diverse populations is needed to validate whether similar segments emerge based on sensitivity to temporal texture and juiciness dynamics. Future studies could further examine how individual differences shape responses to dynamic sensory trajectories across different PBMA formats and consumption contexts.

5. Conclusion

This study combined descriptive sensory analysis (DA) and dynamic consumer profiling (TCATA) to evaluate the temporal evolution of texture performance in plant-based meat analogues (PBMA), with a particular focus on *juiciness* and breakdown behavior during mastication. Across formulations, PBMA showed earlier fragmentation, faster moisture loss, and less sustained *juiciness* compared to the gradual, *fibrous* breakdown of the animal-based reference (ANI), highlighting fundamental differences in temporal texture trajectories rather than static texture intensity alone. Descriptive analysis indicated that protein source (animal vs. plant) was the primary driver of texture differences, while emulsifier concentration had only a minor structuring effect within the plant-based samples. Fat source influenced specific sensory attributes, particularly for attributes such as *dryness*, *granularity*, and *juiciness* stability. Rapeseed-based patties (R0–R20) were generally rated *juicier* and less *dry* than palm-based ones (P0–P20) (Table 3, Fig. 2), although increasing emulsifier level did not significantly enhance *juiciness* in either oil system. The hybrid sample with animal fat (TAL) delayed *dryness* and extended *flavor* persistence. These findings indicate that while emulsion structuring contributes to the matrix, emulsifier concentration alone is not a reliable standalone strategy for improving PBMA *juiciness*. Rather, fat type and overall matrix design emerged as the dominant determinants of temporal juiciness perception.

Temporal sensory tracking (TCATA) provided critical insight into when sensory changes occurred during mastication, capturing the timing and persistence of attributes such as *juiciness*, *dryness*, and particle perception (*grainy* vs *coarse*) that were not fully resolved by chew-point DA alone. This confirms the added value of temporal methods for understanding dynamic texture perception in PBMA.

Consumer segmentation showed that acceptance depends not only on product performance but also on psychographic traits and oral processing style. Meat-attached consumers (Cluster 1) were more sensitive to early *dryness* and *fragmentation*, while flexitarians with lower PBMA rejection (Cluster 3) tolerated *disintegration* and were more open to adoption. A moderate cluster (Cluster 2) showed less texture sensitivity overall, reflecting a neutral stance. These results underscore that there is no single “ideal” PBMA texture: rather, acceptance depends on how temporal sensory trajectories align with consumer expectations and attitudes.

Taken together, DA and TCATA confirmed that fat source and matrix structuring are the primary drivers of *juiciness* during mastication. In the DA results, emulsifier concentration showed a clear linear effect on *juiciness*, *dryness*, and *coating*, confirming that formulation structure strongly influenced the timing and extent of moisture release dynamics. TCATA results, in turn, highlighted fat source as the dominant factor shaping perceived juiciness, with the inclusion of animal fat (TAL) supporting more sustained lubrication over the course of chewing

compared to plant-based formulations. For developers, this highlights the need to optimize fat type and structural design to deliver sustained *lubrication* during mastication. For consumer science, it emphasizes that acceptance is shaped both by the product sensory profiles as they evolve over time and by individual perceptual differences and attitudes toward PBMA.

Informed consent and ethical approval

Ethical approval for this study was obtained from the University of Southern Denmark's Research Ethics Committee (Approval ID RECS20). All participants signed an informed consent prior to participating in the study.

Declaration of generative AI and AI-assisted technologies in the manuscript preparation process

During the preparation of this work the authors used ChatGPT 5 was used to assist in generating R scripts for plotting and data analysis, and Microsoft Copilot 365 was used to improve grammar and overall flow of the text. After using these tools, the authors reviewed and edited the content as needed and take full responsibility for the content of the published article.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Christina J. Birke Rune: Writing – original draft, Visualization, Software, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Arlete Maria Lima Marques:** Writing – review & editing, Methodology, Investigation, Conceptualization. **Mathias Porsmose Clausen:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Methodology, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization. **Davide Giacalone:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Methodology, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization.

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Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foodqual.2026.105986>.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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